

ISic3557

I.Sicily inscription 3557

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Drepanum

Place of origin (modern)

Trapani

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Lost, Museo Pepoli (Trapani) ms. 33 and 221

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: PHI337221

1. Θ (εοῖ) ς Κ (αταχθονίοις)
2. ἰδίῳ συμβίῳ [— —],
3. ὃς ἔζησ[εν] ἔτη [— —]ΟΓ
4. τὸν μνημόσυνον
5. ἐποίησε εὐνοίας
6. καὶ μνήμης ἔνεκεν
7. Ἰουλία Γ[α]μικὴ Ἰχν [α] τ (ία) ²⁶Ἰγνατία(?)²⁶.
- 8.

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 645632

EDCS 71000778

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Bibliography

1923-. Supplementum epigraphicum graecum. *Supplementum epigraphicum graecum*. At 52.0902

Filippi, A. 2002. Trapani: testimonianze storiche ed archeologiche. *Sicilia Archeologica*. 35: 73-87. At 75 no.10/7

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